

1 **The transcriptional landscape of luminal B subtype breast cancer in humans: CHMP5.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Breast cancer in humans is a solid tumor type with distinct subtypes historically defined by the PAM50
7 molecular subtype classification scheme (1-3). We utilize, in this study, whole transcriptome technologies
8 to define the transcriptional landscape of luminal B subtype human breast cancer (4, 5). We describe here
9 differential expression of CHMP5 in luminal B breast cancer.
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1 We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technology, using only primary tumor tissues from
2 patients with breast cancer of defined molecular subtype (4, 5) to perform differential gene expression
3 analyses, for characterization, in molecular detail, of the tumor transcriptome of luminal B subtype breast
4 cancer.

5 **Methods**

6 We utilized microarray datasets GSE45827 (4) and GSE87049 (5) for this global differential gene
7 expression analysis of luminal B subtype human breast cancer in conjunction with the R-based
8 computational differential gene expression software GEO2R. GSE45827 was generated using
9 [HG-U133_Plus_2] Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array technology with $n=11$ normal breast
10 tissues (control) and $n=30$ luminal B subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer; analysis
11 was performed using GPL570. GSE87049 was generated using Affymetrix Human Gene 1.0 ST Array
12 [transcript (gene) version] technology with $n=35$ normal breast tissues (control) $n=27$ primary breast
13 tumors of luminal B subtype from humans with breast cancer; analysis was performed using platform
14 GPL6244. We used an R-based bioinformatic tool to perform whole transcriptome co-regulation studies
15 across multiple tissues (SEEK [6]). We utilized a computational tool to measure the influence of tumor
16 gene expression on overall survival in humans with breast cancer, in $n=1879$ patients (total), in $n=431$
17 basal subtype patients, in $n=596$ luminal A subtype patients, in $n=439$ luminal B subtype patients, in
18 $n=362$ HER2+ patients, and $n=51$ normal-like subtype patients (7).

19 **Rationale**

20 Breast cancer in humans is a complex molecular entity that remains to be completely defined.

21 **Results**

22 We performed whole transcriptome profiling - subtraction analysis, also known as differential gene
23 expression profiling - to identify and describe at the systems level the complete set of genes whose
24 expression was most specifically activated or repressed in humans with the luminal B subtype of human
25 breast cancer.

26 1. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: luminal B subtype

27 $n=11$ normal breast tissues (human)

28 $n=30$ primary tumors (breast; human; luminal B)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
219356_s_at	6.61E-10	-7.9618812	12.30219	-1.7718868	CHMP5	2125/29873	92.9

29 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and luminal B breast
30 tumors, we discovered differential expression of charged multivesicular body protein 5, encoded by
31 CHMP5 (located at 9p13.3) in luminal B breast cancer in humans (Chart 1). The expression of CHMP5
32 changed more than 92% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all
33 transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative
34 fold-change indicating increased quantity of CHMP5 messenger RNA in luminal B subtype tumors,
35 demonstrating up-regulation of CHMP5 during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to
36 luminal B breast cancer.

2. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: luminal B subtype

$n=35$ normal breast tissues (human)

$n=27$ primary tumors (breast; human; luminal B)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8154785	1.26E-17	-11.7978903	29.803562	-1.0361201	CHMP5	123/33297	99.6

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and luminal B breast tumors in a second microarray dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of CHMP5 in luminal B breast cancer in humans (Chart 2). The expression of CHMP5 here changed more than 99% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CHMP5 messenger RNA in luminal B subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CHMP5 during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to luminal B breast cancer.

Thus, CHMP5 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the luminal B breast cancer subtype in humans.

In breast cancer as in any solid tumor, the function of the gene identified by whole transcriptome differential gene expression cannot be assumed to be the same as in non-transformed tissues. Thus, to identify gene products likely to interact with and/or be relevant to the differentially expressed genes function in the transformed tissue, we performed whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation studies using SEEK, an R-based computational tool that blindly and quantitatively identifies co-expression across the genome using a clustering method rather than integration-based differential gene expression methodology (6). This second whole transcriptome technology identified YIPF4, TMED7, SCOC, ARP9 and STXBP3 as the five genes across the transcriptome most closely co-regulated with CHMP5 in the transformed human breast (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed human breast: CHMP5.

1 Finally, we evaluated the influence of CHMP5 tumor gene expression on overall survival (**Figure**
 2 **2**) (7).

17 **Fig. 2: Relationship between CHMP5 tumor expression and overall survival in humans with breast cancer.**
 18 Caption: Overall survival in all patients (above; left), in patients with basal subtype (above; center), in patients with luminal A
 19 subtype (above; right), in patients with luminal B subtype (below; left), in patients with HER2+ subtype (below; center), and
 20 patients with normal-like subtype breast cancer (below; right) is depicted in these Kaplan-Meier plots.

21 **Discussion**

22 We describe here CHMP5 as a component gene product of the luminal B subtype in human breast
 23 cancer, suggesting its importance in the development or maintenance of the subtype, a product of tumor
 24 evolution in transformation of solid tissues in humans.
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